

“The MelArete Project”: Education on Friendship as a Political Virtue for Caring Communities

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Introduction

The human condition rests on an ontological paradox. Humans have no sovereignty over their own being, which is fragile, vulnerable, and fleeting. Simultaneously, they are bound by the responsibility to shape their own becoming, making their existential possibilities flourish. Cultivating the art of existing means learning to accept and take on this responsibility, which is expressed in caring for one’s life. However, to make one’s own life good, it is not enough to care for oneself. One must also be cared for by others (Tronto, 1993; Kittay, 1999; Held, 2006; Mortari, 2022).

Humans are singular beings because each one has an individuality that expresses its unrepeatable originality. However, they are also plural beings, since their ontological consistency is essentially relational. In the human condition, being-there is being-with-others (Heidegger, 1927/2010). Because humans have a plural consistency, the possibility of achieving a good life does not concern humans as individuals, but as beings in relationships with one another. As a fundamental existential phenomenon, care is the modality in which the condition of being-with-others finds an essentially ethical qualification. Reflecting on how to give good form to our living with others means reflecting on how to promote an ethical education for citizenship, so caring relationships can facilitate the flourishing of the community and individuals in their differences and originality.

Specifically, this is the educational purpose of the second edition of the MelArete programme, developed by the Center of Educational and Didactic Research (CRED) of the University of Verona (Italy). After an original implementation focusing on courage, generosity, respect, and justice, starting from the scholastic year 2020-2021, the programme was updated with a specific focus on friendship, conceptualised as an ethical and political virtue, according to the Aristotelian interpretation. The title ‘MelArete’ combines the Greek terms ‘*melete*’ and ‘*arete*,’ which, respectively, mean ‘care’ and ‘virtue,’ the main conceptual cornerstones of the programme, which addresses kindergarten and primary school children.

In this essay, we will 1) outline the theoretical framework on which the programme is rooted, which conceptualises an education on friendship in the perspective disclosed by the philosophy of care and the ethics of virtues; 2) briefly compare the theory underlying MelArete with the main cultures in ethical education presented in the international literature; 3) describe one of the educational activities proposed to the children in the MelArete programme, specifically an activity that fosters their reflection on friendship, sparked by the selected thoughts of important

philosophers; and 4) present and comment on data collected from the implementation of this activity in some Italian kindergarten and primary school classes.

1. *Theoretical Framework: Philosophy of Care and Ethics of Virtue*

MeIArete can be defined as a programme of education on virtues from the perspective of care. Including a reflection on friendship as a political virtue developed to construct caring communities, its second edition gives form to a programme of ethical education for citizenship. Given this definition, some conceptual connections must be clarified: the connection between ethics and care, given the priority of justice in ethical Occidental thought; the connection between care and virtues, given the possibility that the concept of virtue is not framed in a theory of care; the connection between virtues and education, given Socrates' scepticism about the possibility of teaching the virtues; and the connection between friendship and citizenship, given the common consideration of friendship as an elective form of affective relationship.

1.1. *Ethics and Care*

The intimate connection between care and ethics is confirmed in the reflections of Paul Ricœur, renowned for his studies on phenomenology and his contribution to philosophical hermeneutics, who delved into the concepts of ethics and morality in an essay published in 1990. In this essay, after defining ethics as aiming for a good life with and for others in just institutions, Ricœur notices that the term 'aiming' (*souhait* in French) is too generic and suggests substituting it with the term 'care' (*souci* in French). Consequently, 'ethics' is defined as discourse about care for oneself, care for others and care for institutions (Ricœur, 1990). Given this definition, it is possible to establish a connection between ethics and care by concluding that the ethics of a good life must be an ethics of care. However, importantly, in Occidental culture, ethics has been mainly interpreted over time through the concept of justice. Going back to ancient Greek philosophy, in the Socratic and Platonic perspective, justice finds a primary position. This is evident, for example in the following Socratic declaration: "I thought I should run any risk on the side of law and justice rather than join you, for fear of prison or death, when you were engaged in an unjust course" (Plato, *Apology*, 32b-c). In *Gorgias*, Socrates states that the most excellent way of life consists in practicing justice and all other virtue (527e). Because of this primacy, which must be reserved for justice, the main principle to which one must adhere is that "doing what's unjust is more to be guarded against than suffering it" (Plato, *Gorgias*, 527b). The *Republic*, where Plato stages the ideal city, opens with a long discourse about the essence of justice. The importance given to justice leads Socrates to say that if someone "finds many injustices in his life, he awakes from sleep in terror, as children do, and lives in anticipation of bad things to come" (Plato, *Republic*, 330e). Nevertheless, the primacy assigned to justice must be considered from a broader perspective that recognises the practice of caring for the soul as the very core of the Socratic *paideia*. The ancient Greek philosopher Aristotle considers justice a complete virtue because it addresses others (*Nicomachean Ethics*, V, 1129b 25–27) and because every virtue is included in the virtue of justice (*Nicomachean Ethics*, V, 1129b 29–30). However, another virtue addresses others, namely friendship, which he seems to prioritise over justice: "If people are friends, they have no need of justice, but if they are just they need friendship in addition; and the justice that is most just seems to belong to friendship" (Aristotle, *Nicomachean Ethics*, VIII, 1155a 27-29). This position is significant because, according to a phenomenological analysis of the practice of care, friendship results in a virtue in which care

realises itself intensely. Moreover, friendships can be conceptualised as caring relationships (Mortari, 2006, 2016).

A fundamental reference for contemporary ethical reflections can be found in the theory of justice outlined by John Rawls, who considers justice as fairness. His fundamental book, *A Theory of Justice*, was published in 1971. The same year, Milton Mayeroff published an important work about care entitled *On Caring*. According to Rawls (1971), “each person possesses an inviolability founded on justice that even the welfare of society as a whole cannot override” (p. 3). Meanwhile, Mayeroff states that the primary ontological necessity is the one of care that allows a person to actualise herself (1971). Furthermore, according to Rawls (1971), the life of a community must be built on the principle of justice, guaranteeing to everybody the full respect of rights, which are not subjected to political bargaining. In contrast, according to Mayeroff (1971), life must be ordered with principles that inspire us to act with care. In summary, it is possible to state that the theory of justice is based on the ontological premise that a community is constituted by self-sufficient people. However, the theory of care assumes that each constitutively relational person needs others.

During the last decades of the past century, great consideration was devoted to Rawls’s thesis. Nonetheless, growing attention has emerged for the principles shaping an ethics of care, mainly from the cultural perspective disclosed by feminist thought. Carol Gilligan (1982), based on data collected through empirical research, theorises two ethical voices, the “voice of care” and the “voice of justice.” The ethical theory underlying *MeIArete* considers the voices of care and justice as complementary. Indeed, one does not enact good care if what one does is not just. In contrast, one does not act justly if one does not care for the people or things for which one is acting. Returning to ancient Greek philosophy, this complementarity is confirmed in Plato’s *Phaedro*, in which Socrates states that Zeus, who is responsible for the world, has the duty of arranging and caring for all things (246e).

1.2. Care and Virtues

The concept of virtue was born in ancient Greek philosophy. It finds precise theorisation among the Sophists. However, it is with Socrates and Plato and later with Aristotle that the discourse about virtue becomes the object of a deep philosophic examination. Socrates indicates the importance of persuading young people to “care for virtue” (Plato, *Euthydemus*, 275a) and, highlighting the importance of caring for the soul, suggests that from virtue originates the richness needed by the soul to acquire the best possible form (Plato, *Apology*, 30b). In *Apology* (29e), Socrates clarifies that virtue is among the things, along with wisdom and truth, that must be cared for, and he defines his mission as persuading Athenians “to care for virtue” (Plato, *Apology*, 31b). Even in Aristotle’s opinion, virtue is essential for seeking a good quality of life (*eudaimonia*). In this regard, he defines “virtue” as “the sort of state that does the best actions concerning pleasures and pains” (Aristotle, *Nicomachean Ethics*, II, 1104b 27-28). Based on the assumption that searching for good connects to acting according to virtue (Aristotle, *Nicomachean Ethics*, I, 1099a 15–16), Aristotelian ethics can be defined as an ethics of virtues. The concept of virtue is clearly explicated in the *Rhetoric*: “Virtue, it would seem, is a faculty of providing and preserving good things, a faculty productive of many and great benefits, in fact, of all things in all cases” (1366a–b). Virtue becomes crucial when one must act, and every action is guided by an evaluation taking

shape when analysing the situation. The risk is that the analysis and the resultant decision can become unbalanced between the opposite extremes in which a situation occurs. Therefore, the essence of virtue should be found in being able to stay in the mean between the extremes of excess and deficiency: “Virtue, then, is a mean, insofar as it aims at what is intermediate” (Aristotle, *Nicomachean Ethics*, II, 1106b 27-28).

In the classical and mediæval periods, the concept of virtue was central, and it remained important in the post-mediæval and modern periods, when other ways of interpreting ethics emerged. Then, virtue ethics declined during the positivistic–analytical period (Pellegrino & Thomasma, 1993). The concept of virtue has only recently been revived in philosophical debate after having been long forgotten (Foot, 1978). In this renewed interest in virtue ethics, Aristotelian thought plays a central role. According to Nussbaum (2012), this can be explained by an ever-increasing dissatisfaction with certain formalistic ethics, which, being fundamentally interested in guaranteeing moral reasoning of universal value, result in being far from the requirements of practical life. However, according to Berges (2009), the limit of the current rediscovery of the ethics of virtues is that it forgets the contribution of Plato, while a valid and rigorous ethics of virtues cannot prescind from the study of Platonic thought. If it is true that some dialogues are aporetic and fail to completely define the essence of the virtues they examine, they nevertheless present a method for analysing ethical issues.

The theory of ethical education underlying the MelArete programme considers Aristotelian thought as central to the construction of the conceptual framework of an ethics of virtues; likewise, it simultaneously considers the Socratic thought emerging in the Platonic dialogues as essential to interpreting the concept of virtue through the consideration of the concept of care, and to providing precise methodological indications to examine virtues. Another contribution to the theory construing ethical education as an education on virtue from the perspective of care originates from a phenomenological analysis of experiences of care. As a practice, care reveals its essential qualities through the ways of being of a person when one relates to others and to things. Phenomenological research (Mortari & Saiani, 2014; Mortari, 2022) suggests that the ways of being that characterise a good practice of care can be defined using the same concepts through which virtues are referred. Indeed, care is revealed in the thoughts and deeds of generosity, responsibility, patience, courage, respect, justice, gratitude, and so on.

1.3. Virtues and Education

An education in care can result in an education on virtues, given theoretical assumptions about ethical education’s conceptualisation as an education to care and the essential nucleus of care’s comprising virtues. A question arises: Is an education on virtues possible? Doubt is raised in Plato’s *Meno* (96 c–d). The argument is presented that because it is impossible to find teachers of virtues, it must be concluded that virtues cannot be taught. The discussion about the possibility of teaching virtues is also addressed in *Protagoras*, where Socrates highlights that “the wisest and best of our citizens are unable to transmit to others the virtues that they possess” (319e). Subsequently, after stating that he could name many personally good men who could not make anyone else good, he concludes, “Looking at these things, Protagoras, I just don’t think that virtue can be taught” (Plato, *Protagoras*, 320b). If, at first glance, it might seem that Socrates excludes the possibility of an education on virtues, an analysis of the Greek text and the consideration of

the example he offered in the Platonic dialogues lead to reconsidering the issue. In *Meno*, where the possibility of teaching virtue is discussed, the Greek word ‘*didakton*’ is used (89c, 89d, 93b, 96c), which is translatable as ‘teachable.’ Effectively, if we imagine teaching as an instructional action of transmitting something to someone else, virtues cannot be taught, because, as Socrates points out, they cannot be transmitted to others. However, as Socrates exemplifies in his *paideia*, education differs from instruction, which is clear when he states that he never promised to teach anything and has not done so (Plato, *Apology*, 33b). In the Socratic perspective, education is considered a practice of caring for others to make them learn to care for their souls (Plato, *Apology*, 29d–e). This care for the soul is realised by caring for virtues (Plato, *Apology*, 31b 5) because only virtues generate the richness of what life needs (Plato, *Apology*, 30b). Nonetheless, if education is not instruction and virtues are not teachable in that they cannot be transmitted, how is it possible to educate others to care for them? Socrates indicates the educational method in the dialogues, in which he urges his interlocutors to reason about virtues to catch their essence. The importance that Socrates attributes to the practice of reasoning about virtues is clarified in his *Apology*, where he states, “It is the greatest good for a man to discuss virtue every day” (38a). If the quality of an ethical act depends on the rightness of the deliberation on which it is based, then knowledge of what induces decisions is essential. Otherwise, mistakes will be unavoidable (Plato, *Phaedrus*, 237b–c). Correspondingly, reasoning on virtues is fundamental because only by knowing their essence can one make the right ethical choices.

If the method of educating to virtues suggested by the Socratic *paideia* is engagement in eidetic thinking, namely, examining a concept to catch its essential meaning, Aristotle conceives of virtues as a way of being that develops through practice. He states, “We become just by doing just actions, temperate by doing temperate actions, brave by doing brave actions” (Aristotle, *Nicomachean Ethics*, II, 1103b 1-2). In ancient culture, the essential duty of a human comprised learning the technique of existence. Because learning a technique requires practice, it is possible to conclude that a virtuous way of being also takes shape through practice. Precisely because of the centrality given to practice in ethical education, Aristotle states, “It is not unimportant ... to acquire one sort of habit or another, right from our youth” (*Nicomachean Ethics*, II, 1103b 23-25). If it is clear that Socrates highlights the centrality of reasoning while Aristotle suggests the priority of practising, it must be clarified that in their reflections about ethical education, some common elements also exist. According to Socrates, practice, even with a marginal role compared to an eidetic exam, is also important for cultivating virtues. In fact, in the *Republic* he suggests that virtues of the soul require habit and practice (518e). Aristotle does not ignore the role of thinking. He maintains that ethical acting is acting according to the right reasoning (Aristotle, *Nicomachean Ethics*, II, 1103b 33). Indeed, it must be clarified that the Aristotelian concept of virtue as habit, which is at the core of all interpretations of Aristotelian virtue ethics, does not refer to unreflective behaviour but to a way of being that takes shape due to the work of reason (Aristotle, *Nicomachean Ethics*, II, 1105a 28–33). In other words, it must be recognised that acting according to virtues requires the continuous guidance of critical and reflective reason (Pellegrino & Thomasma, 1993).

Given this theoretical framework, the MelArete project utilises a theory of education to virtue from the perspective of care, and according to Socratic and Aristotelian methods. Indeed, in designing the programme, importance has been given to reasoning on ethical concepts and the practice of virtues. However, an issue arose when designing educational activities on the practice of virtues. How can we translate the Aristotelian suggestion of considering the importance of practice without

establishing a priori what constitutes the ethical way of acting in a precise situation? It must be recognised that authentic educational action cannot aspire to shape humans from the outside by imposing predefined ways of behaving. The challenge has been to seek a method that allows children to pay attention to their ethical experiences without directing them in advance. The solution was to design activities that involve children reflecting on ethical practices. In this way, children are not urged to act precisely, but are invited to think about how they and others act.

1.4. Friendship and Citizenship

MelArete, especially in its second edition, can be defined as a project of education on virtues for citizenship because the concept of virtue has ethical and political interpretations. This is true for virtues addressed to others to seek their good and, as a community, to seek the common good. Socrates refers to virtues that are proper for human beings and virtues that are proper for citizens (Plato, *Apology*, 20b). Consequently, it is possible to distinguish personal virtues, which orient the cultivation of the soul and are exercised towards oneself to shape one's being, and political virtues, which concern living with others in the world. Moreover, according to Aristotle, there are virtues exercised towards oneself and virtues exercised towards others. In his opinion, "the best person is not the one who exercises virtue [only] towards himself, but the one who [also] exercises it in relation to another, since this is a difficult task" (Aristotle, *Nicomachean Ethics*, V, 1130a 7–8). Among other virtues exercised towards others which, following the Aristotelian concept, can be interpreted as a political virtue, there is friendship. According to Aristotle, friendship is necessary for life because "no one would choose to live without friends even if he had all the other goods" (*Nicomachean Ethics*, VIII, 1155a 5–6). Socrates states something similar in *Lysis*, where we read, "I would rather have a good friend than the best quail or gamecock known to man, and ... more than any horse or dog. There's no doubt in my mind ... that I would rather possess a friend than all Darius's gold or even than Darius, himself. That's how much I value friends" (211e 2–7). Friendship is necessary for life and important for human flourishing because it enhances ethical development by making people better in reflection and in action (Aristotle, *Nicomachean Ethics*, VIII, 1155a 16). According to Aristotle, three typologies of friendship exist: friendship based on utility, where people "love the other not in his own right, but insofar as they gain some good for themselves from him" (*Nicomachean Ethics*, VIII, 1156a 10–12); friendship based on pleasure, where people "like a witty person not because of his character, but because he is pleasant to them" (*Nicomachean Ethics*, VIII, 1156a 12–14); and ethical (*The Eudemean Ethics*, VII.7, 1241a 10) or complete friendship (*Nicomachean Ethics*, VIII, 1156b 7), where people "wish goods to their friend for the friend's own sake" (*Nicomachean Ethics*, VIII, 1156b 9–10). Good will, which can be conceptualised as the disposition to promote the good of the other, pertains to the last typology of friendship (Aristotle, *The Eudemean Ethics*, VII.7, 1241a 10). Ethical friendship is an important example of a caring relationship because it is nourished by the logic of gifts. The goodwill or benevolence which characterises friendship involves doing "someone a good turn without aiming to receive one in return" (Aristotle, *Nicomachean Ethics*, VIII, 1162b 36–1163a 1). One does not desire good for another due to an ulterior motive or interest; one desires good for another due to one's devotion to him, not for oneself.

What makes Aristotelian reflections particularly interesting for designing experiences of ethical education for citizenship is his interpretation of friendship as a political virtue. This interpretation is clearly argued where he suggests that friendship is fundamental for a community: "Friendship

would seem to hold cities together, and legislators would seem to be more concerned about it than about justice. For concord would seem to be similar to friendship, and they aim at concord among all, while they try above all to expel civil conflict, which is enmity” (Aristotle, *Nicomachean Ethics*, VIII, 1155a 22–26). This concept is also taken up in *The Eudemian Ethics*, where Aristotle states that “the promotion of friendship is regarded as the special task of the political skill” (VII.1, 1234b 23). Since friendship is considered the basis for building and maintaining a community, an education in it must conceive of it as an indispensable aspect of ethical education for citizenship. Indeed, the cohabiting that—according to the philosophy of care—essentially characterises our being in the world needs justice and concord, a feeling that takes shape precisely in friendships. This is why it can be hypothesised that the solidaristic and supportive network of living together that shapes a community finds a promising and fruitful strengthening in diffusion of friendships. A society that cultivates the greatest possible relational meaningfulness is one in which schools aim to form citizens willing to collaborate in respect of and in appreciation for each other’s differences for the common good. This disposition, on which programmes on an ethical education for citizenship should centre, can be called “political friendship” (Aristotle, *Nicomachean Ethics*, IX, 1167b 2). Political friendship is fundamental for living in a community seeking for and engaging in the common good because people who cannot cultivate citizenship from the perspective of political friendship “seek to over-reach in benefits [to themselves] and shirk labours and public services. And since each wishes this for himself, he interrogates and obstructs his neighbour; for when people do not look out for the common good, it is ruined” (Aristotle, *Nicomachean Ethics*, IX, 1167b 11–14).

Based on this theoretical framework, which conceptualises friendship as a fundamental ethical virtue for caring relationships and an essential political virtue for caring citizenship, the MelArete programme involves children in educational activities designed to give them the opportunity to reflect on what friendship is and how it takes form in their lives.

2. Literature Overview: Approaches to Ethical Education

A literature review on ethical education makes clear that different pedagogical cultures have been developed in this field. In particular, the majority of authors refer to character education, in its traditional form or in its current forms, the cognitive–developmental approach or moral reasoning, and care ethics education (Howard, Berkowitz & Schaeffer, 2004; Althof & Berkowitz, 2006; Graham, Haidt, & Rimm-Kaufman, 2008; Cooley, 2008). Character education, in its traditional form, was developed in the United States at the end of the 19th century. Through the first four decades of the 20th century, it was characterised by its purpose of instilling traditional values and inculcating desirable habits in youth. In the 1960s, after a period of vacuum in this field, a renewed interest in promoting ethical education in schools emerged with the appearance of the values clarification movement, which declined under criticism of being relativistic and lacking scientific evidence regarding its impact. The 1970s and early 1980s were dominated by the cognitive–developmental approach, which raised criticisms about the appropriateness of inculcating a predefined set of virtues and, relying on Kohlberg’s research on the stages of moral development, was instead interested in promoting moral reasoning through discussions about moral dilemmas (Kohlberg, 1975; Kohlberg & Hersh, 1977; Turiel & Rothman, 1972; Rest, 1980; Nucci, 1985). The cultural dominance of the cognitive–developmental approach decreased in the late 1980s and 1990s under the criticism of feminist theorists, who emphasised the importance of caring

relationships, empathic responses and moral sentiments, which are stressed and promoted by care ethics education (Noddings, 1984, 1988, 2002a, 2002b 2010a, 2010b, 2016; Noddings & Slote, 2002; Slote, 2010).

In recent decades, we are seeing a return to character education, an expression that nowadays is often used as an umbrella for varied approaches and methodologies to foster personal development, encompassing educational purposes related to moral reasoning, social-emotional learning, citizenship education, risk behaviour prevention and many other endeavors (Otten, 2000; Pattaro, 2016). As character education, in its current form, remains difficult to define because existing approaches refer to distinct philosophical frameworks, pedagogical strategies and outcome goals (Althof & Berkowitz, 2006), it could be useful to directly give voice to associations and authors that recognise themselves in this pedagogical culture. According to Lickona (1991), character education is “the deliberate effort to develop a good character based on core virtues that are good for the individual and good for society” (p. 228). The Character Education Partnership asserts it is fostering “the deliberative effort by schools, families and communities to help young people understand, care about and act upon core ethical values” (cited in Lickona, 1996, p. 93). According to the ASCD, the Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development, character education includes “any deliberate approach by which school personnel, often in conjunction with parents and community members, help children and youth become caring, principled and responsible” (cited in Singh, 2019, p. 3). As per Howard, Berkowitz and Schaeffer (2004), it is “an attempt to prepare individuals to make ethical judgments and to act on them, that is, to do what one thinks ought to be done” (p. 189). As for the Jubilee Centre (2022), it “includes all explicit and implicit educational activities that help young people to develop positive personal strengths called virtues” and “is about helping pupils grasp what is ethically important in situations and how to act for the right reasons, so that they become more autonomous and reflective in the practice of virtue” (p. 7). Watts, Fullard and Peterson (2021) state that it is “the conscious process of cultivating worthwhile and positive dispositions” that they call “character virtues or character strengths” (p. 12).

The last two decades have been characterised by an important effort to rigorously study the effectiveness of character education programmes, so the literature refers to the aspiration to a “science of character education” (Berkowitz, 2002; Berkowitz, Bier & McCauley, 2017). Based on research on what works in character education, Berkowitz (2021) proposes six “design principles for how to nurture the development of human goodness, as well as other parts of human growth and academic learning” (p. 3); in clarifying these principles, the author uses the acronym PRIMED, which refers to the following elements: prioritization of character education, relationships, intrinsic motivation, modelling, empowerment, and developmental pedagogy. Kristjánsson (2015) directly refers to Aristotle to outline “a theoretical account of character education—as a form of moral education focusing on the development of virtues—designed along broadly Aristotelian lines” (p. 2). From this perspective, virtues are believed necessary for human flourishing.

Comparing the theory of ethical education underlying *MeIArete* with the several approaches outlined in the literature is not the focus of this essay and would require a broader space. Nonetheless, we can try to clarify commonalities and differences. Similar to character education, *MeIArete* considers virtues central to ethical education, but without confusing education with

indoctrination, as happened in the traditional form of this approach. Indeed, like the cognitive–developmental approach, MelArete gives importance to the development of reasoning and the encouragement of critical thinking by involving students in discussing ethical dilemmas, but without falling into abstractionism or rationalism as do some activities in this educational ethical approach. Similar to care ethics education, MelArete assigns a primary value to care but creates distance from an interpretation of care that is too situational or pre-eminently affective, because it considers care a practice informed both by emotions and thoughts, and considers the position that decisions in situations are also oriented by general principles, primarily obedience to the needs that reality reveals. Unlike current character education approaches, MelArete does not refer to the concept of character. Indeed, it refers to virtues as the essential ethical nucleus of care. Even if it is not defined as a character education programme, it embraces the call for research to evaluate the effectiveness of educational activities. Hence, data are collected in the classes involved in the programme, and they are analysed through qualitative methods to study the effectiveness of the proposed educational activities in fostering children’s ethical thinking (Mortari & Valbusa, 2019; Mortari et al., 2023; Mortari, Valbusa & Ubbiali, 2023; Mortari, Ubbiali & Bombieri, 2023). Finally, even if MelArete shares the importance of conceiving an education on virtues as fundamental for human flourishing, it diverges from Aristotelian character education because it does not take Aristotle as its main theoretical reference, but integrates Aristotelian and Socratic ethical thoughts and frames the cultivation of virtues in the theoretical perspective disclosed by the philosophy of care.

3. The Educational Programme: An Activity Designed to Reflect on Friendship

Grounded in this theoretical framework, the MelArete educational programme was designed to involve children in reflecting upon ethical concepts and experiences. The educational purposes of the curricula designed for kindergartens and primary schools are the same. However, some differentiations in activities are introduced according to the ages of the students involved. The main educational instruments used are as follows:

- Socratic conversations: children are invited to reason together on the essential meaning of ethical concepts and virtues, such as those suggested by words such as ‘good,’ ‘care,’ and ‘friendship.’ The researcher, acting as a facilitator, guides the conversation by asking questions to help children better clarify, deepen and problematise their ideas, to encourage a co-construction of thinking within the class.
- Stories: narrations exemplifying virtues, such as generosity and respect, are presented to children to encourage their reflection on the virtuous actions of the characters, which are animals living in the ‘Wood of Virtues.’ In kindergarten, stories are animated with puppets, while in primary school, they are handed to children on an illustrated sheet and read by the researcher. Furthermore, in kindergarten, reflections on stories are conducted together through a conversation, starting from some questions posed by the researcher. In primary school, before sharing their reflections through a conversation, children are required to answer some questions individually in written form.
- Vignettes: Ethical dilemmas are presented in graphical form to involve children in discussions about what is the virtuous way, for example the courageous way or the just way, to act in a precise situation. The situations illustrated in the vignettes

differ in kindergarten and primary school. In the first case, characters are animals, while in the second case, they are humans. Furthermore, in primary school, children also engage in a written individual activity before discussion.

- Experiential diary: children are invited to keep a personal journal where they collect their own thoughts on or consider gestures of gratitude. This virtue was added to the others on which the programme focused because to reflect on experiences of gratitude allows one to reflect on the experiences of good that one receives and that nourish life.

Furthermore, within the programme, a particular activity has been organised entitled “The Thoughts of the Sages” in primary school and “The Wise Animals of the Wood” in kindergarten. This activity encourages children to reflect on the concept and experience of friendship, starting from some philosophical ideas about it. In designing the activity, some philosophers’ sentences on friendship were selected and, in some cases, reformulated in easier language to facilitate children’s understanding. In primary school, these philosophical sentences are bound inside a notebook given to the children. On each page is a cartoon of a philosopher who states his/her idea. Beside it is a space where each child, individually, is asked to answer in writing the question: “What do you think about this?” Each child is invited to choose and comment on at least two of the philosophers’ thoughts. Subsequently, children are encouraged to discuss them, also considering the conceptualisations of friendship that they supplied through previous activities. In kindergarten, the organisation is quite different because the conversational activity about the philosophers’ ideas is included in a ludic frame. The researchers hide puppets of animals from the “Wood of Virtues” in the school hall or garden. The puppets hold jars between their paws, inside which are philosophical sentences on friendship. After a brief introduction, the researchers invite the children to look for the animals and bring the jars to the centre of the classroom. Next, the jars are opened, and researchers read the philosophers’ ideas to the children. For each philosophical sentence, a conversation is conducted starting from the following questions: “Do you agree with this sentence? Why? What do you think?” At the end of the conversation, the researchers propose that the children make a group drawing of a gesture of friendship.

The philosophical sentences proposed to the children are as follows:

- Socrates: “I would rather have a friend than all the gold of the richest man in the world” in primary school; “It is more important to have a friend than to have a treasure” in kindergarten (see Plato, *Lysis*, 211e 2–7, reformulated sentences).
- Aristotle: “No one would choose to live without friends even if he had all the other goods” (*Nicomachean Ethics*, VIII, 1155a 5–6).
- Pythagoras: “Friends have all in common” (see Turner, 1947, pp. 380–381).
- Epicurus: “The wise man suffers for his friend’s pain as much as he suffers for his own pain. And for a friend, he is ready to do anything, even to die, because if he betrays his friend, his life will be disrupted by his infidelity” in primary school; “The wise man suffers for his friend’s pain as much as he suffers for his own pain” in kindergarten (see *Vatican Sayings* 56 and D.L. 10. 121, reformulated sentences).
- Seneca: “From an enemy a friend may derive” (see *Epistulae morales ad Lucilium*, 95, 63, reformulated sentence).

- Cicero: “A true friend is seen in times of trouble” (see *De amicitia*, XVII, 64, reformulated sentence).
- Simone Weil: “Do not wish that someone gives you their friendship: Act as a friend towards them” (see Weil, 1970/2015, p. 43, reformulated sentence).

During the conversation about these philosophical sentences on friendship, the researchers take care that the conversational climate is also characterised by friendship. Therefore, children are invited to respect others in their persons and thoughts, to wait for their turn to speak, to listen and pay attention to others’ ideas and to recognise the value of dialogue, since it is an opportunity for cognitive enrichment and personal development.

4. *Friendship in Children’s Ideas*

The research implemented to study the educational effectiveness of the MelArete programme has confirmed that the activity presented above can stimulate children to reflect on the concept and experience of friendship, illustrating interesting and profound ideas. Indeed, philosophical sentences are an effective starting point to encourage them to reflect and discuss with each other, even trying to mediate between different perspectives. In this regard, it will be interesting to present some children’s ideas, collected during the implementation of the activity in two classes of two kindergartens and two classes of two primary schools in the south of Italy, with the involvement of 4-5-6-year-old and 10-11-year-old students.

Reflecting on the Socratic sentence in the kindergarten, a child commented that “friends are always close and always hold hands.” According to him, friendship is important because it answers the human needs of others. It is the condition that allows us not to be alone. Other children highlighted that friendship is important because it allows people to have fun: “I agree [with Socrates] because friends are for fun”; “With friends, we always have fun and play.” According to another child, “it is better to have money” because, in his opinion, with money, one can buy toys. Another comrade added, “You can buy TV, PlayStation games to play with your cousins.” Then, the researcher asked, “Is it better to have lots of toys or lots of friends?” A child, showing the effort to mediate between the different positions that emerged in the conversation, replied, “I like to play together.” This answer suggests that having games is beautiful. However, the best condition is having the opportunity to use them with friends.

In a primary school class, the reasoning developed among the children is that money is finite. On the other hand, friendships “do not finish” and “are infinite,” they said. At that point, the researcher asked, “And if you have a fight with a friend, what happens?” One child replied, “You can always remedy it afterwards.” Another explained how it is possible to remedy, i.e., “by apologising or by making a kind gesture to the other person.” Agreeing with the Socratic idea, a child clarified that a friend can brighten your day: “Instead with money, that is gold, you cannot do anything if you are sad.” According to these ideas, friendship improves one’s quality of life.

Reflecting on the Aristotelian sentence, a child in primary school commented, “I do not like this judgment, because a person even without friends can be happy through family or maybe cousins....” According to him, it is important to emphasise that not only friendship ties, but also family ties make a happy life. Another child highlighted that what Aristotle means is that “his life, without

friends, is meaningless.” His classmate added that “what Aristotle says is right because having friends means happiness in life.”

In kindergarten, a conversation arose about the possibility of conceiving of pets as friends. One child said, “I always hug my cat. I love him.” Another replied, “It doesn’t help having a cat; he scratches you.” So the first child reiterated, “Even if he scratches me, I love him anyway.” This dialogical exchange is significant because, starting from the children’s reflections, one could open the question about our relationship with animals: What relationship do we feel we must have with animals for a good quality of life? Are animals part of or outside of the human world? If they are part of the human world because we are inside the world of nature, how should our relationship with nature be cultivated? It is an ethical and political question because it concerns ways to live together and with other beings in a shared environment.

Discussing Pythagoras’s sentence, children in kindergarten seemed to interpret the idea of having everything in common as having the same interests and doing something together. For example, one said, “Friends play together.” Another interpretation that emerged during the conversation among kindergarten children concerns the idea of sharing something. In this regard, one child said, “If one has two snacks and a classmate does not have a snack, he gives him the other one.” The researcher then raised the following question: “And if he has only one?” The answer that emerged was “He divides into two.”

The primary school children, commenting on Pythagoras’s sentence, also referred to play, though they noted that children do not always have the same desires regarding which game to play. In such cases, friendship consists of trying to mediate between positions: “According to me, they don’t have all in common, because ... for example, I want to play ‘hide and seek,’ while [my friend] wants to play another game. These games are combined.” In addition, another child added, “For example, you want to play ‘hide and seek.’ I want to play ‘dodge ball,’ and ... we play while I hide, and you with the ball have to hit me.”

Dialoguing Epicurus’s sentence, in kindergarten a conversation arose about events during which a friend falls and gets hurt. In these cases, according to some children, “you must cure him” and “you care for and cure him.” When the researcher asked how one feels when seeing a friend who has been hurt, the children responded that they were “sad” and “worried.” In primary school, one child raised the possibility that a friend is suffering because of an offense, and stated, “For example, if you offend one of your friends, you and he feel bad because you realise that you were wrong.” Another child referred to the reciprocity that could characterise a friendship: “Maybe if you help a friend, when you are in a bad situation, your friend helps you, maybe with words that can make you feel good.”

As is evident, the children’s reflections are not always a strict interpretation of the philosophical sentences presented to them. However, for the involved children, the philosophical sentences become the starting point for reflecting on friendship according to their thoughts and experiences. Discussing Seneca’s sentence, the kindergarteners considered situations in which one quarrels with a friend: “When [a classmate] argues with me, then we make peace, and she becomes a good friend.” In addition, “I get angry, but then I make peace.” The children’s experience of friendship as it

emerges from these thoughts suggests that difficult relationships can be transformed into good ones.

In primary school, a discussion arose on the term ‘may’ in the sentence “Seneca says that from an enemy may derive a friend.” “It is not sure,” said a child. In addition, another child stated, “In my opinion ... that may be that he is sure because maybe it is an encouragement to the people who read him.” During the dialogical exchanges, a political reflection about the coexistence of peoples emerged regarding what happens when they are involved in a war, which is bad because it also breaks relational bonds. In particular, a child said, “If a people is at war ... maybe there were these two children who were from different peoples and went to school together. Then, in this war, they were divided. A person, if he is in that war situation, cannot become [a] friend again because war is ugly; one does ugly things.” Indeed, this child is reasoning about the situation opposite to the one considered by Seneca. That is, he is reflecting on the possibility that two people who are friends can become enemies. A classmate clarified, “Yes, but if they went to the same school and were already friends, then the friendship was already born and therefore means they were not enemies.”

Commenting on Cicero’s sentence, the kindergarteners shared experiences that corroborated the presented philosophical idea. For example, one child, who was afraid of the dark, said that when it is dark, he runs away. Then, the researcher asks: “What would a friend do when it’s dark?” The child answers: “He would turn on the light.” Other children connect the need for friendship with the need for care: “A true friend cares for you”; “when you get hurt, a friend comes to cure you.” Another child clarified that a friend supports her in moments of sadness. Referring to a classmate, she said, “She always consoles me when I cry.”

A similar thought emerged in primary school, where a child highlighted, “You need a shoulder to lean on here, that is, because you know he will help you through this bad time, and you need that friend.” In this statement, the child suggested the need to have a friend in a difficult life moment to avoid bearing such moments alone.

In kindergarten, the conversation about the sentence of Simone Weil was encouraged by the researcher through the question, “How do you become friends?” A child answered, “You become friends ... when you go to someone’s house, love each other and play together.” This thought highlights that friendship arises when people share spaces of life and interests, when they spend time and do things together, and when the relationship is nourished by affection.

In primary school, a child interpreted Simone Weil’s sentence this way: “Friendships are not given as gifts; they are created.” Other children found in the presented philosophical idea an opportunity to reflect on the importance of taking the first step to re-establish a friendly relationship when quarrelling: “If you quarrel with someone, you don’t wait for him to apologise, but you go directly to tell [sorry] to him,” said a child.

Thoughts and experiences highlighted by children in their comments to the philosophical sentences make clear that friendship is considered important to enhancing one’s quality of life and to establishing positive and supportive relationships for the construction of caring communities.

In conclusion, we can state that involving children in reflecting on friendship is not only necessary, as the theoretical framework outlined above made clear, but also possible, as the empirical data have shown.

Conclusion

This article has presented the MelArete project, which is structured on a theory of ethical education conceived as education to virtue in the perspective of care and, consistently, in an educational programme aimed at involving kindergarten and primary school children in reflecting on ethical concepts and experiences.

While preserving the dialogue with the main traditions of ethical education explored in international literature, the theoretical framework on which the MelArete project is based reveals its own originality and innovativeness, particularly in its integration of the Socratic and Aristotelian perspectives about virtue education and in its conceptualization of virtue education within the theoretical horizon disclosed by the philosophy of care. As argued, the focus on friendship makes the second edition of MelArete a project of ethical education for citizenship. Indeed, in line with Aristotle's interpretation, friendship is understood as a political virtue, capable of nurturing caring relationships that foster the flourishing not only of individuals but also of the community.

The MelArete programme designed for kindergarten and primary school children is strictly grounded in the presented theoretical framework. Among the activities designed to engage students in reflecting about the concept and experience of virtues, there is the one presented in this article, which encourages children to think about friendship based on the thoughts of some philosophers. The ideas collected through this activity show the richness of the involved children's ethical thinking, as they were able to engage in dialogue with the presented philosophers, drawing important insights from the philosophical sentences to conceptualize friendship starting from their own experience. In the conversations among students who reflected together on the philosophers' sentences, the process of conceptualization was a co-constructive process, in which each child contributed to the construction of the ideas of friendship by listening to others' perspectives as well as by expressing his or her own, in a mutual enrichment of thought.

The theoretical and empirical parts of this article should be considered closely related: in fact, if the theory of ethical education underlying the MelArete project argues why ethical education is important, the presented educational activity, which is focused on the specific virtue of friendship, shows how ethical education to virtues in the perspective of care can be concretely implemented.

The second edition of the MelArete project is still being implemented in other Italian kindergarten and primary school classrooms, and research is being conducted on the various promoted activities, with the aim to evaluate the program based on a rigorous analysis of the collected data. This article is not the place to delve into the heuristic aspects related to the empirical study we are conducting, but the findings that have emerged so far confirm the effectiveness of the programme in promoting the expression and development of children's ethical thinking. In this article, we have focused on the presentation of some of the children's ideas emerging from the specific activity we described,

with the intention also to show the richness and depth of the involved students' ethical thinking in dialogue with the philosophers' selected sentences about friendship.

Friendship is an important experience in children's lives, and encouraging their reflection on it as a virtue, including its significance as a political virtue capable of nurturing caring relationships and communities, is essential to fostering the development of their ethical awareness. The MelArete project aims to reach this goal by bringing ethical education into schools, a privileged place to promote reflection on relationships, care for the others, and the common good.

References

- Althof, W., & Berkowitz, M. W. (2006). Moral education and character education: Their relationship and roles in citizenship education. *Journal of Moral Education* 35 (4), pp. 495-518.
- Aristotle. (1999). *Nicomachean ethics*. 2nd ed. Hackett Publishing Company.
- . (2011). *The eudemian ethics*. Oxford University Press.
- . (2022) *Rhetoric*. Good Press.
- Berges, S. (2009). *Plato on virtue and the law*. Continuum.
- Berkowitz, M. W. (2002). The science of character education. *Bringing in a New Era in Character Education* 508, pp. 43-63.
- . (2021). *PRIMED for character education: Six design principles for school improvement*. Routledge.
- Berkowitz, M. W., Bier, M. C., & McCauley, B. (2017). Toward a science of character education. *Journal of Character Education* 13 (1), pp. 33-51.
- Cooley, A. (2008). Legislating character: Moral education in North Carolina's public schools. *Educational Studies* 43 (3), pp. 188-205.
- Foot, P. (1978). *Virtues and vices and other essays in moral philosophy*. Basil Blackwell.
- Gilligan, C. (1982). *Different voice*. Harvard University Press.
- Graham, J., Haidt, J., & Rimm-Kaufman, S. E. (2008). Ideology and intuition in moral education. *International Journal of Developmental Science* 2 (3), pp. 269-286.
- Heidegger, M. (1927/2010). *Being and time*. State University of New York Press.
- Held, V. (2006). *The ethics of care: Personal, political, and global*. Oxford University Press.
- Howard, R. W., Berkowitz, M. W., & Schaeffer, E. F. (2004). Politics of character education. *Educational Policy* 18 (1), pp. 188-215.
- Jubilee Centre for Character and Virtues. (2022). *A framework for character education in schools*. 3rd ed. University of Birmingham.

- Kittay, E. (1999). *Love's labor: Essays on women, equality, and dependency*. Routledge.
- Kohlberg, L. (1975). The cognitive-developmental approach to moral education. *The Phi Delta Kappan* 56 (10), pp. 670-677.
- Kohlberg, L., & Hersh, R. H. (1977). Moral development: A review of the theory. *Theory into Practice* 16 (2), pp. 53-59.
- Kristjánsson, K. (2015). *Aristotelian character education*. Routledge.
- Lickona, T. (1991). *Educating for character*. Bantam.
- . (1996). Eleven principles of effective character education. *Journal of Moral Education* 25 (1), pp. 93-100.
- Mayeroff M. (1971). *On caring*. Harper Collins Publishers.
- Mortari, L. (2006). *La pratica dell'aver cura*. Bruno Mondadori.
- . (2016). For a pedagogy of care. *Philosophy Study* 6 (8), pp. 455-463.
- . (2022). *The philosophy of care*. Berlin: Springer VS.
- Mortari, L., & Saiani, L. (eds.). (2014). *Gestures and thoughts of caring*. McGraw-Hill Education.
- Mortari, L., Ubbiali, M., & Bombieri, R. (2023). Dialoguing on friendship as political virtue: An experience of citizenship education for primary school children. In M. Carmo (Ed.), *Education and new developments 2023* (pp. 57-61). inScience Press.
- Mortari, L., & Valbusa, F. (2019). Exploring children's ethical thinking: What virtues are and how they can be learned. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences* 9 (12), pp. 128-135.
- Mortari, L., Valbusa, F., & Ubbiali, M. (2023). MelArete project: Theory and practice of a kindergarten and primary school program for ethical education. In M. Carmo (d.), *Education and new developments 2023* (pp. 27-31). inScience Press.
- Mortari, L., Valbusa, F., Ubbiali, M., & Bombieri, R. (2023). The empirical phenomenological method: Theoretical foundation and research applications. *Social Sciences* 12 (7), pp. 413. <https://doi.org/10.3390/socsci12070413>. Accessed 20 July 2025.
- Noddings, N. (1984). *Caring: A feminine approach to ethics and moral education*. University of California Press.

- . (1988). An ethic of caring and its implications for instructional arrangements. *American Journal of Education* 96 (2), pp. 215-230.
- . (2002a). *Educating moral people: A caring alternative to character education*. Teachers College Press.
- . (2002b). *Starting at home: Caring and social policy*. University of California Press.
- . (2010a). Moral education and caring. *Theory and Research in Education* 8 (2), pp. 145-151.
- . (2010b). Moral education in an age of globalization. *Educational Philosophy and Theory* 42 (4), pp. 390-396.
- . (2016). Moral life and education. *Action in Teacher Education* 38 (3), pp. 212-216.
- Noddings, N., & Slote, M. (2002). Changing notions of the moral and of moral education. In N. Blake, P. Smeyers, R. Smith, & P. Standish (eds.). *The Blackwell guide to the philosophy of education* (pp. 341-355). Blackwell.
- Nucci, L. (1985). Future directions in research on children's moral reasoning and moral education. *Elementary School Guidance & Counseling* 19 (4), pp. 272-282.
- Nussbaum, M. (2012). Non-relative virtues: An Aristotelian approach. In G. Sher (ed.). *Ethics: Essential readings in moral theories* (pp. 446-459). Routledge.
- Otten, E. H. (2000). *Character education*. ERIC Digest. ERIC Clearinghouse for Social Studies/Social Science Education.
- Pattaro, C. (2016). Character education: Themes and researches: An academic literature review. *Italian Journal of Sociology of Education* 8 (1), pp. 6-30.
- Pellegrino, E.D., & Thomasma, D. C. (1993). *The virtues in medical practice*. Oxford University Press.
- Plato. (1997). *Complete works*. Hackett Publishing Company.
- Rawls, J. (1971). *Theory of justice*. Harvard University Press.
- Rest, J. R. (1980). Moral judgment research and the cognitive-developmental approach to moral education. *The Personnel and Guidance Journal* 58 (9), pp. 602-605.
- Ricœur, P. (1990). Ethique et morale. *Revista Portuguesa de Filosofia* 46 (1), pp. 5-17.
- Rist, J. M. (1980). Epicurus on friendship. *Classical Philology* 75 (2), pp. 121-129.

- Singh, B. (2019). Character education in the 21st century. *Journal of Social Studies (JSS)* 15 (1), pp. 1-12.
- Slote, M. (2010). Sentimentalist moral education. *Theory and Research in Education* 8 (2), pp. 125-143.
- Tronto, J. (1993). *Moral boundaries*. Routledge.
- Turiel, E., & Rothman, G. R. (1972). The influence of reasoning on behavioral choices at different stages of moral development. *Child Development* 43 (3), pp. 741-756.
- Turner, J. H. (1947). Epicurus and friendship. *The Classical Journal* 42 (6), pp. 351-356.
- Watts, P., Fullard, M., & Peterson, A. (2021). *Understanding character education: Approaches, applications and issues*. Open University Press.
- Weil, S. (2015). *First and last notebooks*. Wipf and Stock Publisher.